

INVARIANT CAUSAL SET COVERING MACHINES

Thibaud Godon*
Université Laval

Baptiste Bauvin
Université Laval

Pascal Germain
Université Laval

Jacques Corbeil
Université Laval

Alexandre Drouin
ServiceNow Research

ABSTRACT

Rule-based models, such as decision trees, appeal to practitioners due to their interpretable nature. However, the learning algorithms that produce such models are often vulnerable to spurious associations, and thus, they are not guaranteed to extract causally relevant insights. This limitation reduces their utility in gaining mechanistic insights into a phenomenon of interest. In this work, we build on ideas from the invariant causal prediction literature to propose *Invariant Causal Set Covering Machines*, an extension of the classical Set Covering Machine (SCM) algorithm for conjunctions/disjunctions of binary-valued rules that provably avoids spurious associations. The proposed method leverages structural assumptions about the functional form of such models, enabling an algorithm that identifies the causal parents of a variable of interest in polynomial time. We demonstrate the validity and efficiency of our approach through a simulation study and highlight its favorable performance compared to SCM in uncovering causal variables across real-world datasets.

1 INTRODUCTION

In some fields of application of machine learning, the use of learned models goes well beyond prediction. Domain experts often rely on a deeper inspection of such models to extract mechanistic insights into complex systems. For instance, in healthcare, one can train a model to predict predisposition to a disease based on genomics data (Szymczak et al., 2009). Significant insights can then be obtained by understanding which genomic traits are used for prediction (biomarkers). These constitute potential causes of the disease, which might be relevant targets in the elaboration of new therapies or drugs.

One kind of machine learning model that has been shown to allow for such scrutiny is rule-based models, such as decision trees (Breiman et al., 1984). Such models make inferences by applying a series of binary-valued rules to their input (e.g., the presence or absence of a mutation). In addition to their high level of interpretability, such models have been shown to scale particularly well to large feature sets and resist overfitting in the small data regime that is common in applications of machine learning to healthcare (Drouin et al., 2019). However, one must not be fooled by the ease of interpretation of such models, since the variables used for prediction may very well be spuriously associated with the outcome of interest.

In this work, we make a step towards alleviating this issue by proposing *Invariant Causal Set Covering Machines*, an extension of the Set Covering Machine algorithm (Marchand & Shawe-Taylor, 2002) for conjunctive and disjunctive classifiers, that avoids, as much as possible, relying on spurious associations for prediction. Our work builds on previous advances in invariant causal prediction (Peters et al., 2016; Heinze-Deml et al., 2018; Bühlmann, 2020), where data is assumed to be collected in multiple environments (e.g., populations from different geographic locations, measurement devices with different calibrations, etc.).

Contributions: (1) We propose Invariant Causal Set Covering Machines (ICSCM), an extension of the Set Covering Machine algorithm (Marchand & Shawe-Taylor, 2002) that relies on invariant causal prediction to avoid spurious associations (Section 3). (2) We support this new algorithm with theoretical results expressing conditions under which the causal parents of an outcome of interest can be recovered in polynomial time (Theorem 3.1). (3) We conduct a brief empirical study with simulated data to verify the correctness of the theory and the efficiency of the algorithm (Section 4).

*thibaud.godon.1@ulaval.ca

2 BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

We consider a standard supervised binary classification setting, where the observations are feature-label pairs (\mathbf{x}, y) , with $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}$ and $y \in \{0, 1\}$. Further, as in Heinze-Deml et al. (2018), we consider the case where the observations have been collected in multiple environments $e \in \mathcal{E}$, which correspond to various experimental conditions (e.g., populations from different geographic locations, measurement devices with different calibrations, etc.). Hence, we assume access to observations $(\mathbf{x}, y, e) \sim P(\mathbf{X}, Y, E)$, where the data-generating process P factorizes according to G depicted at Fig. 1a. The random variable \mathbf{X} is segmented as $\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{X}_A, \mathbf{X}_B, \mathbf{X}_C]$, respectively denoting the causal parents of Y , variables that are not directly related to Y , and the causal children of Y . Formally, we make four assumptions, are common in the causal discovery literature (see Glymour et al., 2019), presented in section A.1.

Goal: We aim to learn a classifier $h : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$, such that $h(\mathbf{x}) = h(\mathbf{x}_A) = y$ with high probability, i.e., that closely approximates Y while relying solely on its *causal parents* \mathbf{X}_A and no other *spurious association*.

We now introduce the Set Covering Machine (SCM) algorithm (Marchand & Shawe-Taylor, 2002), which can be used to learn classifiers that are conjunctive in nature. Later on, at Section 3, we will explain how this algorithm can be extended to achieve the goal defined above.

Let (\mathbf{x}, y) be a pair of features and binary label, as described at previously. The SCM algorithm is a greedy learning algorithm that attempts to find the shortest conjunction or disjunction $h_{\text{conj}}(\mathbf{x}) = r_1(\mathbf{x}) \wedge \dots \wedge r_d(\mathbf{x})$ where the r_i are binary-valued rules, that minimizes the expected prediction error. The pseudocode for learning such a conjunction is presented in A.2.

The SCM algorithm is a simple and efficient way of learning interpretable conjunctive classifiers. However, it has one significant pitfall: nothing prevents $h(\mathbf{x})$ from relying on spurious associations between \mathbf{X} and Y . In Section 3, we set out to alleviate this issue.

The two most related works from the causal inference literature are the seminal works of Peters et al. (2016) and Heinze-Deml et al. (2018) on invariant causal prediction. Both of these works rely on a multi-environment setting like the one described earlier. Moreover, both are based on the idea that the conditional distribution of Y , given all of its causal parents \mathbf{X}_A , should be invariant across environments; an idea that we also exploit in Section 3. In contrast with our work, Peters et al. (2016) require the structural equation between Y and \mathbf{X}_A to be linear, while we assume it to be conjunctive (see Assumption A.4). As for Heinze-Deml et al. (2018), they consider non-linear structural equations, which are compatible with our setting. However, identifying \mathbf{X}_A using their approach requires to perform conditional independence tests for all sets of potential parents, which requires $O(2^{|\mathbf{X}|})$ time, where $|\mathbf{X}|$ is the number of feature variables (see Section 2). In sharp contrast, we show that, by exploiting the conjunctive nature of the structural equation of Y , the causal parents \mathbf{X}_A can be identified in polynomial time.

3 INVARIANT CAUSAL SET COVERING MACHINES

We now propose an extension of the classical Set Covering Machine algorithm that exploits invariances across environments (see Assumption A.3) to learn classifiers that rely solely on the causal parents \mathbf{X}_A of Y .

Tree-based representation: To facilitate the presentation, let us introduce an alternative perspective on conjunctions. Let $f(x) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} r_1(x) \wedge \dots \wedge r_d(x)$ be an arbitrary conjunction of binary-valued rules r_i applied to some input x . If one assumes an ordering in the evaluation of the rules $r_i(x)$, then $f(x)$ corresponds to a simple decision tree composed of a single branch. This is illustrated at Fig. 1b. Such a tree has d *negative leaves* where $f(x) = 0$, which are attained when a rule $r_i(x) = 0$, and a single *positive leaf* where $f(x) = 1$, which is attained when $r_i(x) = 1 \forall i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$.

With this perspective in mind, we propose the following theoretical result.

Theorem 3.1. (*Model construction criteria*) Assume that the data-generating process follows the causal graph depicted at Fig. 1a and that Assumptions A.1, A.2, A.3, and A.4 hold. Let $f(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon) = g(r_1(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_1) \wedge \dots \wedge r_d(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_d), \epsilon_g)$, with $\mathbf{X}^* \subseteq \mathbf{X}$, be an arbitrary conjunction of d binary-valued

rules. Without loss of generality, assume an arbitrary ordering of the rules $1 \dots d$ and consider the tree-based representation depicted in Fig. 1b. We have that, if:

i) the distribution of Y in the i -th negative leaf satisfies

$$Y \perp_P E \mid \mathbf{b}_{<i}(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_{<i}) = \mathbf{1}, r_i(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_i) = 0, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{b}_{<i}(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_{<i}) = \mathbf{1}$ denotes that all rules preceding r_i in the ordering have value 1, and

ii) the distribution of Y in the positive leaf satisfies

$$Y \perp_P E \mid \mathbf{b}_{<d}(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_{<d}) = \mathbf{1}, r_d(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_d) = 1, \quad (2)$$

then $\mathbf{X}_A \subseteq \mathbf{X}^*$ and $\mathbf{X}_C \cap \mathbf{X}^* = \emptyset$.

The proof exploits the conjunctive nature of f (see App. A.4).

Model construction: Theorem 3.1 gives us criteria that can be evaluated at each step of building a conjunction and guarantee reliance on all \mathbf{X}_A but none of the \mathbf{X}_C . That is, we can simply modify Algorithm 1 to i) disregard all rules where Criterion (1) is not satisfied when searching for the rule of maximal utility and ii) continue adding rules to the conjunction until Criterion (2) is satisfied. A detailed pseudocode and implementation details are given at Algorithm 1.

However, note that Theorem 3.1 does not guarantee the *minimality* of \mathbf{X}^* , i.e., Criteria (1) and (2) could be satisfied even if $\mathbf{X}_B \cap \mathbf{X}^* \neq \emptyset$. Hence, we propose the following pruning procedure, which can be applied as long as none of the rules r_i jointly relies on elements from both \mathbf{X}_A and \mathbf{X}_B . For example, this holds in the common setting where the rules are threshold functions on the value of a single feature.

Proposition 3.2. (Pruning) Assume that Assumptions A.1 and A.2 hold. Let $f(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon)$ be a conjunction that satisfies Equations 1 and 2, but is non-minimal, i.e., $\mathbf{X}_B \cap \mathbf{X}^* \neq \emptyset$. For any $\mathbf{X}^\dagger \in \mathbf{X}^*$, we have that $Y \perp_P E \mid \mathbf{X}^* \setminus \mathbf{X}^\dagger$ if and only if $\mathbf{X}^\dagger \notin \mathbf{X}_A$.

Hence, the $f(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon)$ can be pruned, iteratively, by applying a conditional independence test to each $\mathbf{X}^\dagger \in \mathbf{X}^*$ and removing any rule that makes use of non-causal-parents of Y . The proof is given at App. A.5.

Invariant Causal Set Covering Machines: By combining the construction Criteria (1) and (2) with Proposition 3.2, we obtain a simple modification of the Set Covering Machine algorithm that can provably *identify* all the causal parents \mathbf{X}_A of Y . Of note, the runtime complexity is $O(m \cdot |\mathcal{R}| \cdot n)$, where $|\mathcal{R}|$ is typically linear w.r.t. $|\mathbf{X}|$. This is in sharp contrast with the exponential runtime complexity of non-linear ICP.

(a) Identification of the causal parents \mathbf{X}_A : proportion of 100 training runs where the model relied solely on \mathbf{X}_A , for an increasing number of distractor features \mathbf{X}_B (1–7). Worst values coloured.

Model	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
SCM	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
DT	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
ICP	0.96	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.09	0.00
ICSCM	0.96	0.97	0.99	0.96	0.97	0.96	0.96

(b) Running time w.r.t. the size of \mathbf{X}_B .

Figure 2: Side-by-side comparison of identification accuracy (Table (a)) and runtime (Figure (b)).

4 EXPERIMENTS

We start by conducting experiments in a controlled setting, with simulated data that is guaranteed to satisfy the assumptions of our method. We then compare the ICSCM to its “non-causal” variant, SCM, on real-world datasets in which our assumptions are unlikely to hold completely.

Simulated data samples are generated from a discrete Bayesian network comprises two causal parents $\mathbf{X}_A = [X_{A1}, X_{A2}]$, a single descendant \mathbf{X}_C that is a stronger predictor of the target Y than the causal parents, and a set of distractor variables \mathbf{X}_B whose cardinality varies from 1 to 7. This setting is detailed in App. A.6. Baselines include the Set Covering Machines (SCM; Marchand & Shawe-Taylor (2002)), decision trees (DT; Breiman et al. (1984)), and non-linear ICP (ICP; Heinze-Deml et al. (2018)). ICP should be robust to spurious associations, while DT and SCM should not. Fig. 2a shows that SCM and DT consistently rely on spurious correlations and fail to recover the true causal parents \mathbf{X}_A , whereas both ICP and our proposed **ICSCM** correctly identify \mathbf{X}_A in the majority of settings. Notably, ICP’s performance deteriorates as dimensionality increases due to a loss of statistical power in its conditional-independence tests, while ICSCM remains largely unaffected even with several hundred variables (this observation is discussed in section A.11). In terms of computational complexity, ICSCM scales linearly with the number of variables, in stark contrast to the exponential growth observed for ICP (Fig. 2b), rendering ICSCM far more suitable for high-dimensional real-world applications.

In the second phase we evaluate the algorithms on six real-world datasets drawn from the Tablesift benchmark (Hardt & Kim, 2022). All experimental details are provided in App. A.7 Each dataset provides a known set of causal features for the target Y and defines two environments (in-distribution vs. out-of-distribution). Models are built from simple rule candidates (thresholds on individual features) with a maximum conjunction size of $n = 10$, and each experiment is repeated 20 times. Results are presented in Fig. 4. For $n = 10$, ICSCM selects a larger number of genuine causal features than SCM in four out of six datasets and also exceeds a random-selection baseline in most cases. Although SCM yields slightly higher predictive accuracy—reflecting the well-known trade-off between causal interpretability and pure prediction performance—the gap is modest. Consequently, even when the stringent theoretical assumptions are violated in practice, augmenting SCM with causal constraints substantially improves the discovery of truly causal variables.

5 CONCLUSION

This work introduced ICSCM, a learning algorithm that builds conjunctive and disjunctive models that, in some settings, are guaranteed to rely exclusively on the causal parents of a variable of interest. The algorithm is supported by a rigorous theoretical foundation that exploits invariances that hold in a multi-environment setting to avoid spurious associations. In contrast with previous work, such as non-linear ICP (Heinze-Deml et al., 2018), ICSCM leverages a functional form assumption to considerably reduce the number of statistical tests required, leading to a polynomial-time algorithm that is more amenable to practical applications. Results on simulated data support the validity of the proposed algorithm and theory, and results on real-world datasets suggest that it is better at identifying causal variables than the original SCM algorithm. In future work, we will consider relaxations of the current assumptions (e.g., variants of graph G , unobserved confounding), explore the generalization of our approach to decision tree and random forest predictors, and further explore applications to real-world problems where our assumptions are likely to hold.

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A APPENDIX

A.1 PROBLEM SETTING

We consider a standard supervised binary classification setting, where the observations are feature-label pairs (\mathbf{x}, y) , with $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}$ and $y \in \{0, 1\}$. Further, as in Heinze-Deml et al. (2018), we consider the case where the observations have been collected in multiple environments $e \in \mathcal{E}$, which correspond to various experimental conditions (e.g., populations from different geographic locations, measurement devices with different calibrations, etc.). Hence, we assume access to observations $(\mathbf{x}, y, e) \sim P(\mathbf{X}, Y, E)$, where the data-generating process P factorizes according to G depicted at Fig. 1a. The random variable \mathbf{X} is segmented as $\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{X}_A, \mathbf{X}_B, \mathbf{X}_C]$, respectively denoting the causal parents of Y , variables that are not directly related to Y , and the causal children of Y . Formally, we make 4 assumptions, which are common in the causal discovery literature (see Glymour et al., 2019):

Assumption A.1. (*Causal Markov assumption*) We assume that d -separation¹ in G implies conditional independence in P , i.e., for arbitrary random variables U, V, W :

$$U \perp_G V \mid W \Rightarrow U \perp_P V \mid W,$$

where \perp_G denotes d -separation and \perp_P denotes independence in distribution.

Assumption A.2. (*Faithfulness assumption*) For arbitrary random variables U, V, W :

$$U \perp_P V \mid W \Rightarrow U \perp_G V \mid W.$$

Further, we assume that the environments are defined as follows, matching the setting of Heinze-Deml et al. (2018).

Assumption A.3. (*Environments*) The environment E is a causal parent of \mathbf{X} , but it is not a causal parent of Y (see Fig. 1a). In other words, the structural equation $Y := f(\mathbf{X}_A, \epsilon)$, with noise $\epsilon \perp_P \mathbf{X}_A$, is invariant across environments.

Intuitively, this means that the distribution of features \mathbf{X} can change across environments, but the mechanism that produces Y from its causal parents \mathbf{X}_A must remain stable.

Goal: We aim to learn a classifier $h : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$, such that $h(\mathbf{x}) = h(\mathbf{x}_A) = y$ with high probability, i.e., that closely approximates Y while relying solely on its *causal parents* \mathbf{X}_A and no other *spurious association*.

Moreover, we are interested in learning classifiers that are conjunctive in nature, so we make the following additional assumption on the functional form of $Y := f(\mathbf{X}_A, \epsilon)$:

Assumption A.4. (*Functional form*) The function f is s.t.

$$f(\mathbf{X}_A, \epsilon) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} g(r_1(\mathbf{X}_A, \epsilon_1) \wedge \dots \wedge r_d(\mathbf{X}_A, \epsilon_d), \epsilon_g), \quad (3)$$

where $\langle r_1, \dots, r_d \rangle$ are arbitrary binary-valued rules (e.g., threshold functions on the value of features), $\epsilon := \langle \epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_d, \epsilon_g \rangle$ are noise terms sampled from arbitrary independent distributions, and g is a function that tampers with the outcome based on ϵ_g .

A.2 SET COVERING MACHINES

We now introduce the Set Covering Machine (SCM) algorithm² (Marchand & Shawe-Taylor, 2002), which can be used to learn classifiers that are conjunctive in nature. Later on, at Section 3, we will explain how this algorithm can be extended to achieve the goal defined at Section 2.

Let (\mathbf{x}, y) be a pair of features and binary label, as described at Section 2. The SCM algorithm is a greedy learning algorithm that attempts to find the shortest conjunction or disjunction,

$$\begin{aligned} h_{\text{conj}}(\mathbf{x}) &= r_1(\mathbf{x}) \wedge \dots \wedge r_d(\mathbf{x}) \\ \text{or } h_{\text{disj}}(\mathbf{x}) &= r_1(\mathbf{x}) \vee \dots \vee r_d(\mathbf{x}), \end{aligned}$$

¹See Koller & Friedman (2009) (Chap. 3) for an introduction.

²Not to be confused with *Structural Causal Models*. This low-probability clash is unfortunately beyond our control.

Algorithm 1 Set Covering Machine

Input: $\mathcal{S} = \{(\mathbf{x}_i, y_i, e_i)\}_{i=1}^m$, a data sample
Input: \mathcal{R} , a set of candidate binary-valued rules
Input: $p \in \mathbb{R}^+$, utility score hyperparameter
Input: $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, conjunction length hyperparameter
 $\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \{(\mathbf{x}, y) \in \mathcal{S} \mid y = 1\}$ ▷ Positive examples
 $\mathcal{N} \leftarrow \{(\mathbf{x}, y) \in \mathcal{S} \mid y = 0\}$ ▷ Negative examples
 $\mathcal{H} \leftarrow \emptyset$ ▷ Rules in the conjunction
while $|\mathcal{H}| < n$ and $\mathcal{N} \neq \emptyset$ **do**
 for each rule $r_i \in \mathcal{R}$ **do**
 $\mathcal{A}_i \leftarrow \{(\mathbf{x}, y) \in \mathcal{N} \mid r_i(\mathbf{x}) = y\}$ ▷ True negatives
 $\mathcal{B}_i \leftarrow \{(\mathbf{x}, y) \in \mathcal{P} \mid r_i(\mathbf{x}) \neq y\}$ ▷ False negatives
 $U_i \leftarrow |\mathcal{A}_i| - p \cdot |\mathcal{B}_i|$ ▷ Utility computation
 end for
 $i^* \leftarrow \operatorname{argmax}_{1 \leq i \leq |\mathcal{R}|} U_i$
 $\mathcal{H} \leftarrow \mathcal{H} \cup \{r_{i^*}\}$ ▷ Add best utility rule to the model
 $\mathcal{N} \leftarrow \mathcal{N} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{i^*}$ ▷ Remove final samples
 $\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \mathcal{P} \setminus \mathcal{B}_{i^*}$
end while
Output: the conjunction $h(x) = \bigwedge_{r \in \mathcal{H}} r(x)$

where the r_i are binary-valued rules, that minimizes the expected prediction error:

$$\operatorname{Err}_P(h) = \mathbb{E}_{(\mathbf{x}, y) \sim P(\mathbf{X}, Y)} I[h(\mathbf{x}) \neq y],$$

where $I[\text{True}] = 1$ and 0 otherwise.

For conciseness, the rest of the presentation will focus on learning conjunctions ($h := h_{\text{conj}}$). This is not restrictive since any algorithm for learning conjunctions can also be applied to learning disjunctions by the simple application of De Morgan’s law, i.e., $\neg(r_1(\mathbf{x}) \wedge r_2(\mathbf{x})) = \neg r_1(\mathbf{x}) \vee \neg r_2(\mathbf{x})$. Hence, all the forthcoming findings and observations equally apply to the case of learning disjunctions.

Algorithm 1 shows the pseudocode for learning a conjunction with the SCM algorithm. The algorithm starts with a data sample $\mathcal{S} = \{(\mathbf{x}_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^m \sim P(\mathbf{X}, Y)^m$ and a set \mathcal{R} of candidate binary-valued rules. It builds a conjunction by iteratively adding rules $r_i \in \mathcal{R}$. At each iteration, the best rule is selected based on a utility score U_i , which is a tradeoff between the number of negative examples correctly classified (i.e., covered by the rule³) and the number of positive examples misclassified by the rule. Then, the examples for which the model’s outcome is settled (i.e., $h(\mathbf{x}) = 0$) are discarded, and the next iteration is performed considering the examples that remain to be classified.⁴ The training stops when no negative examples remain to cover or when the maximum conjunction length n , which is a hyperparameter, is reached. Overall, the running time complexity of this algorithm is $O(m \cdot |\mathcal{R}| \cdot n)$.

The SCM algorithm is thus a simple and efficient way of learning conjunctive classifiers that minimize the expected prediction error. These predictive models have the benefit of being highly interpretable since their decision function is simple, and they typically rely on a few rules that can be inspected by domain experts (e.g., as in Drouin et al., 2019). However, it has one significant pitfall: nothing prevents $h(\mathbf{x})$ from relying on spurious associations between \mathbf{X} and Y . In Section 3, we set out to alleviate this issue.

³Hence the name: Set *Covering* Machines

⁴Since h is a conjunction, $h(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ if any $r_i(\mathbf{x}) = 0$. The outcome of the model cannot be changed by subsequent rules.

A.3 MODEL CONSTRUCTION

Theorem 3.1 gives us criteria that can be evaluated at each step of building a conjunction and that guarantee reliance on all \mathbf{X}_A but none of the \mathbf{X}_C . We thus propose to modify the original SCM algorithm to

- (i) prevent adding rules to the conjunction that would contradict the property of Eq. (1); and
- (ii) stop adding rules to the conjunction when the property of Eq. (2) is satisfied.

The above criteria (i) and (ii) can be evaluated by statistical independence tests, up to some significance level $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^+$, which is a hyperparameter of our proposed algorithm. Note that, in our experiments, we use a chi-squared (χ^2) hypothesis test with $\alpha = 0.05$.

Applying Criterion (i). Consider the inner loop of Algorithm 1: Let $k=|\mathcal{H}|$ be the number of rules previously added to the conjunction, $r_i \in \mathcal{R}$ be a candidate rule, and $(\mathbf{x}_j^{(i)}, y_j^{(i)}, e_j^{(i)}) \in \mathcal{A}_i \cup \mathcal{B}_i$ denote the samples that would belong to a newly added negative leaf if r_i were added to the conjunction. Denoting with $k' = k + 1$, we have

$$(y_j^{(i)}, e_j^{(i)}) \sim Y \times E \mid \mathbf{b}_{<k'}(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_{<k'}) = \mathbf{1}, r_{k'}(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_{k'}) = 0.$$

To implement Criterion (i), we simply disregard the rule r_i if the p-value of a statistical independence test between the observed $y_j^{(i)}$ and $e_j^{(i)}$ from $\mathcal{A}_i \cup \mathcal{B}_i$ is lower than the threshold α . Among the remaining rules, the one with the maximum utility score U_i is added to the model.

Applying Criterion (ii). Consider the end of the outer loop of Algorithm 1. Let $k'=|\mathcal{H}|$ be the number of rules after the best rule r_{i^*} is added to the model. Then, the samples $(\mathbf{x}'_j, y'_j, e'_j) \in \mathcal{P} \cup \mathcal{N}$ belong to the newly created positive leaf. We have

$$(y'_j, e'_j) \sim Y \times E \mid \mathbf{b}_{<k'}(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_{<k'}) = \mathbf{1}, r_{k'}(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_{k'}) = 1.$$

To implement Criterion (ii), we stop adding rules to the model (i.e., we exit the *while* loop) when the p-value of a statistical independence test between the observed y'_j and e'_j from $\mathcal{P} \cup \mathcal{N}$ is greater than the threshold α .

A.4 PROOF OF THEOREM 3.1

Theorem A.5. *thm:leafs (Model construction criteria) Assume that the data-generating process follows the causal graph depicted at Fig. 1a and that Assumptions A.1, A.2, A.3, and A.4 hold. Let $f(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon) = g(r_1(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_1) \wedge \dots \wedge r_d(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_d), \epsilon_g)$, with $\mathbf{X}^* \subseteq \mathbf{X}$, be an arbitrary conjunction of d binary-valued rules. Without loss of generality, assume an arbitrary ordering of the rules $1 \dots d$ and consider the tree-based representation depicted in Fig. 1b. We have that, if:*

i) the distribution of Y in the i -th negative leaf satisfies:

$$Y \perp\!\!\!\perp_P E \mid \mathbf{b}_{<i}(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_{<i}) = \mathbf{1}, r_i(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_i) = 0, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{b}_{<i}(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_{<i}) = \mathbf{1}$ denotes that all rules preceding r_i in the ordering have value 1, and

ii) the distribution of Y in the positive leaf satisfies:

$$Y \perp\!\!\!\perp_P E \mid \mathbf{b}_{<d}(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_{<d}) = \mathbf{1}, r_d(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_d) = 1, \quad (5)$$

then we have that $\mathbf{X}_A \subseteq \mathbf{X}^*$ and $\mathbf{X}_C \cap \mathbf{X}^* = \emptyset$.

Proof. The proof is divided in two cases and we proceed by contradiction. For simplicity, we use R_i to denote the random variable $r_i(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon_i)$ and will abuse the notation by using r_i to denote a value taken on by R_i .

Algorithm 2 Invariant Causal Set Covering Machine

Input: $S = \{(\mathbf{x}_i, y_i, e_i)\}_{i=1}^m$, a data sample
Input: \mathcal{R} , a set of candidate binary-valued rules
Input: $p \in \mathbb{R}^+$, utility score hyperparameter
Input: $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, conjunction length hyperparameter
Input: $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^+$, independence threshold hyperparameter

$\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \{(\mathbf{x}, y, e) \in S \mid y = 1\}$ ▷ Positive examples
 $\mathcal{N} \leftarrow \{(\mathbf{x}, y, e) \in S \mid y = 0\}$ ▷ Negative examples
 $\mathcal{H} \leftarrow \emptyset$ ▷ Rules in the conjunction
 $\gamma \leftarrow 1$ ▷ A stopping criterion indicator

while $|\mathcal{H}| < n$ and $\mathcal{N} \neq \emptyset$ and $\gamma < \alpha$ **do**

for each rule $r_i \in \mathcal{R}$ **do**

$\mathcal{A}_i \leftarrow \{(\mathbf{x}, y, e) \in \mathcal{N} \mid r_i(\mathbf{x}) = y\}$ ▷ True negatives
 $\mathcal{B}_i \leftarrow \{(\mathbf{x}, y, e) \in \mathcal{P} \mid r_i(\mathbf{x}) \neq y\}$ ▷ False negatives
 $\pi \leftarrow$ p-value of a **independence test** between $y_j^{(i)}$ and $e_j^{(i)}$ from $\mathcal{A}_i \cup \mathcal{B}_i$. ▷ App. A.3, Criterion (i)
 $U_i \leftarrow (|\mathcal{A}_i| - p \cdot |\mathcal{B}_i|)$ **if** $\pi > \alpha$ **else** $-\infty$

end for

$i^* \leftarrow \operatorname{argmax}_{1 \leq i \leq |\mathcal{R}|} U_i$

if $U_{i^*} = -\infty$ **then break** ▷ Stop adding rules

$\mathcal{H} \leftarrow \mathcal{H} \cup \{r_{i^*}\}$ ▷ Add best utility rule to the model
 $\mathcal{N} \leftarrow \mathcal{N} \setminus \mathcal{A}_{i^*}$ ▷ Remove final samples
 $\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \mathcal{P} \setminus \mathcal{B}_{i^*}$

$\gamma \leftarrow$ p-value of a **statistical test** between y'_j and e'_j from $\mathcal{P} \cup \mathcal{N}$. ▷ App. A.3, Criterion (ii)

end while

[Optionally] Conduct pruning according to the procedure described at Proposition 3.2.

Output: the conjunction $h(x) = \bigwedge_{r \in \mathcal{H}} r(x)$

Case 1: Suppose that the properties at Eq. (4) and Eq. (5) hold, but that $\mathbf{X}_A \not\subseteq \mathbf{X}^*$. We have that $\mathbf{X}_A \not\subseteq \mathbf{X}^*$ and thus some of the causal parents of Y are not in \mathbf{X}^* , i.e., there exists $X_{A_i} \in \mathbf{X}_A$ such that $X_{A_i} \notin \mathbf{X}^*$. Hence, we have that $Y \not\perp_P E \mid \mathbf{X}^*$, because there exists an unblocked path $E \rightarrow X_{A_i} \rightarrow Y$. Because \mathbf{X}^* contains all the causal parents of R_1, \dots, R_d , we also have that $Y \perp_P E \mid R_1, \dots, R_d$. By the definition of conditional dependence, this means that $\exists y, e, r_1, \dots, r_d$ such that $P(Y = y \mid R_1 = r_1, \dots, R_d = r_d, E = e) \neq P(Y = y \mid R_1 = r_1, \dots, R_d = r_d)$. Recall that, given the conjunctive nature of $f(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon)$, each combination of r_1, \dots, r_d corresponds to a leaf in the conjunction (see Fig. 1b). Therefore, depending on the value of r_1, \dots, r_d , we will reach a contradiction for either a negative or a positive leaf:

- **Negative leaves:** $\exists j, r_j = 0$, then we have that $P(Y \mid R_1 = 1, \dots, R_{j-1} = 1, R_j = 0, E = e) \neq P(Y \mid R_1 = 1, \dots, R_{j-1} = 1, R_j = 0)$, this is in contradiction with Eq. (4).
- **Positive leaf:** $\forall j, r_j = 1$, then we have that $P(Y = y \mid R_1 = 1, \dots, R_d = 1, E = e) \neq P(Y = y \mid R_1 = 1, \dots, R_d = 1)$, this is in contradiction with Eq. (5).

Case 2: Suppose that the properties at Eq. (4) and Eq. (5) hold, but that $\mathbf{X}_C \cap \mathbf{X}^* \neq \emptyset$. There are some descendants of Y in \mathbf{X}^* , i.e., there exists $X_{C_i} \in \mathbf{X}_C$ such that $X_{C_i} \in \mathbf{X}^*$. Recall, from our graphical assumptions (see Fig. 1a), the existence of the v-structure $Y \rightarrow X_C \leftarrow E$. Since, $X_{C_i} \in \mathbf{X}^*$, there exists at least one R_j such that $X_{C_i} \rightarrow R_j$. Because conditioning on R_j opens the path $E - X_{C_i} - Y$, we have that $Y \not\perp_P E \mid R_1, \dots, R_d$.

By the definition of conditional dependence, this means that $\exists y, e, r_1, \dots, r_d$ such that $P(Y = y \mid R_1 = r_1, \dots, R_d = r_d, E = e) \neq P(Y = y \mid R_1 = r_1, \dots, R_d = r_d)$. Recall that, given the conjunctive nature of $f(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon)$, each combination of r_1, \dots, r_d corresponds to a leaf in the conjunction (see Fig. 1b). Therefore, depending on the value of r_1, \dots, r_d , we will reach a contradiction for either a negative or a positive leaf:

Figure 3: Implicit variables for binary-valued rules: this figure shows an expanded version of the causal graph illustrated in Fig. 1a where the rules in the conjunction (see Eq. (3)) are represented as random variables that mediate all paths from \mathbf{X}_A to Y .

- **Negative leaves:** $\exists k, r_k = 0$, then we have that $P(Y | R_1 = 1, \dots, R_{k-1} = 1, R_k = 0, E = e) \neq P(Y | R_1 = 1, \dots, R_{k-1} = 1, R_k = 0)$, this is in contradiction with Eq. (4).
- **Positive leaf:** $\forall k, r_k = 1$, then we have that $P(Y = y | R_1 = r_1, \dots, R_d = r_d, E = e) \neq P(Y = y | R_1 = 1, \dots, R_d = 1)$, this is in contradiction with Eq. (5).

□

A.5 PROOF OF PROPOSITION 3.2

Proposition A.6. *prop:pruning (Pruning) Assume that Assumptions A.1 and A.2 hold. Let $f(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon)$ be a conjunction that satisfies Equations (1) and (2), but is non-minimal, i.e., $\mathbf{X}_B \cap \mathbf{X}^* \neq \emptyset$. For any $\mathbf{X}^\dagger \in \mathbf{X}^*$, we have that $Y \perp_P E | \mathbf{X}^* \setminus \mathbf{X}^\dagger$ if and only if $\mathbf{X}^\dagger \not\subseteq \mathbf{X}_A$.*

Proof. Since $f(\mathbf{X}^*, \epsilon)$ satisfies Equations (1) and (2), we know that $\mathbf{X}_A \subseteq \mathbf{X}^*$ and $\mathbf{X}_C \cap \mathbf{X}^* = \emptyset$. We now consider two cases. First, let us reason about sufficiency and show that $Y \perp_P E | \mathbf{X}^* \setminus \mathbf{X}^\dagger \Rightarrow \mathbf{X}^\dagger \not\subseteq \mathbf{X}_A$. This follows directly from the faithfulness assumption (Assumption A.2), since taking \mathbf{X}^\dagger from \mathbf{X}_A would open at least one path from E to Y in G (see Fig. 1a), contradicting the conditional independence statement. Second, let us reason about necessity and show that $\mathbf{X}^\dagger \not\subseteq \mathbf{X}_A \Rightarrow Y \perp_P E | \mathbf{X}^* \setminus \mathbf{X}^\dagger$. This follows directly from the causal Markov assumption (Assumption A.1) since removing an element of \mathbf{X}_B leaves all paths in G from E to Y blocked. □

A.6 VALIDATING THE THEORY IN SIMULATION

Data: We parametrize a discrete Bayesian network that satisfies the assumptions at App. A.1. We define two causal parents $\mathbf{X}_A = [X_{A1}, X_{A2}]$ and a single descendent \mathbf{X}_C for Y . We let \mathbf{X}_B be a distractor, unrelated to Y and vary the number of distractors, $|\mathbf{X}_B|$, throughout the experiments. Of particular note, the Bayesian network is designed such that the relationship between Y and \mathbf{X}_C is less noisy than the relationship between Y and its causal parents \mathbf{X}_A . As such, algorithms that are vulnerable to spurious associations will tend to use \mathbf{X}_C instead of \mathbf{X}_A .

More precisely, we define two environments ($\mathcal{E} = \{0, 1\}$), each one contains 10^4 observations. For each observation, the causal parent variables X_{A1} and X_{A2} are $\{0, 1\}$ -valued (binary) randomly

Table 1: Characteristics of the real-world datasets. The first column indicates the number of samples. The second column shows the total number of variables, followed by the number of causal variables among them (in parentheses).

	# samples	# variables (# causal)
acsfoodstamps	840 582	239 (137)
acsincome	1 664 500	232 (66)
assistsments	2 667 776	26 (20)
college scorecard	124 699	118 (11)
diabetes readmission	99 493	183 (37)
meps	26 402	3 595 (120)

generated according to

$$P(X_{A_1}=1|E=0) = 0.1, \quad P(X_{A_1}=1|E=1) = 0.5;$$

$$P(X_{A_2}=1|E=0) = 0.5, \quad P(X_{A_2}=1|E=1) = 0.3.$$

Note that the environment E affects \mathbf{X}_A by changing the distributions of X_{A_1} and X_{A_2} . Conformably to Assumption A.4, the value of $Y \in \{0, 1\}$ is generated as follows (rules r_1 and r_2 are identities, and $\epsilon_y = 0.05$):

$$Y = g_y(r_1(\mathbf{X}_A, \epsilon_1) \wedge r_2(\mathbf{X}_A, \epsilon_2), \epsilon_y)$$

$$= g_y(X_{A_1} \wedge X_{A_2}, \epsilon_y)$$

$$= tv + (1-t)X_{A_1} \wedge X_{A_2}, \text{ with } t \sim \text{Ber}(\epsilon_y), v \sim \text{Ber}(0.5)$$

Hence, Y depends only on its causal parents and not directly on E .

Then, $X_C = (1-u)Y + uE$, with $u \sim \text{Ber}(0.05)$. This reflects the effect of both Y and E on \mathbf{X}_C . Of note, X_C is a better predictor of Y than $X_{A_1} \wedge X_{A_2}$, because even if the noise term $u = 1$, X_C can still have the same value as Y when $E = Y$.

Finally, the variables in \mathbf{X}_B are generated as random variables $X_{B_i} \sim \text{Ber}(\frac{1}{2})^{|X_B|}$. The experiments are conducted with $|X_B|$ ranging from 1 to 7.

Baselines: The baselines that we consider are Set Covering Machines (SCM; Marchand & Shawe-Taylor (2002)), decision trees (DT; Breiman et al. (1984)), and non-linear ICP (ICP; Heinze-Deml et al. (2018)). ICP should be robust to spurious associations, while DT and SCM should not. See App. A.9 for implementation details.

Identification of causal parents: Fig. 2a compares the ability of all methods to identify the causal parents \mathbf{X}_A of Y . As expected, SCM and DT always rely on spurious associations and fail to identify \mathbf{X}_A . On the contrary, both ICP and ICSCM succeed at identifying \mathbf{X}_A in most cases. The performance of ICP degrades as dimensionality increases, likely due to type II errors that arise due to the vanishing statistical power of its conditional independence tests. In contrast, ICSCM appears less affected by dimensionality; this seems to hold even up to hundreds of variables (see Table 4 in the supplementary material). In App. A.11, we report additional results that support these claims and provide an extensive discussion on the effect of type I and II errors on both methods. Finally, it is clear from these results that ICSCM endows SCM with the ability to identify causal parents, which was the main objective of this work.

Runtime complexity analysis: Fig. 2b shows the running time of all methods with respect to dimensionality. Clearly, that of ICP increases exponentially fast, while that of ICSCM increases linearly, as expected in Section 3. This makes it more amenable to real-world applications where variables are plentiful, provided, of course, that our functional form assumption (Assumption A.4) realistically holds.

A.7 EVALUATION ON REAL-WORLD DATA

The previous results support the theoretical soundness of our algorithm. However, they do not assess the method in the wild, where its assumptions are not guaranteed to hold.

Table 2: Prediction errors averaged over the 20 splits. The values on the test set are followed by the value on the train set in parentheses. The standard deviations are given in Table 3.

	SCM	ICSCM
acsfoodstamps	0.19 (0.19)	0.19 (0.19)
acsincome	0.27 (0.27)	0.32 (0.32)
assistments	0.07 (0.07)	0.11 (0.11)
college scorecard	0.08 (0.08)	0.11 (0.11)
diabetes readmission	0.38 (0.38)	0.46 (0.46)
meps	0.27 (0.26)	0.34 (0.33)

Data: We, therefore, conduct an empirical study on six real-world datasets from the tableshift benchmark (Hardt & Kim, 2022). For each of these, we have access to a list of variables known to be causes (\mathbf{X}_A) of the target label (Y), among many other features, as defined in Nastl & Hardt (2024). Moreover, we use Nastl & Hardt (2024)’s notion of “in distribution” and “out of distribution” to define two environments (E) for each dataset. Note, however, that we have no guarantee that the hypotheses presented in Section 2 and Fig. 1a hold, as is common in real-world settings. For example, the relationship between Y and E may be confounded, or the relationship between \mathbf{X}_A and Y may not be a conjunction, among others, which makes for a challenging benchmark.

The datasets, which we now outline, are summarized in Table 1. The “ACS Foodstamps” dataset describes people (U.S. citizens) by socioeconomic variables. The task is to predict Foodstamps reciprocity, and the environment is based on geographical location (U.S. census Divisions). The “ACS Income” dataset describes people (U.S. citizens, employed adults) by socioeconomic variables. The task is to predict whether their income is “high” or “low”, and the environment is based on geographical location (U.S. census Divisions). The “ASSISTments” dataset describes school problems in an online learning tool and a student attempting to solve them. The task is to predict whether the student solves the problem, and the environment is defined based on the school of the student. The “College scorecard” dataset describes United States colleges. The task is to predict the completion rate of students and the environments are defined based on the type of college (Carnegie classification). The “Diabetes readmission” dataset describes patients with medical information. The task is to predict whether the patients will return to a hospital later; the environment is defined based on the hospital of first admission. The “MEPS” (Medical Expenditure Panel Survey) dataset describes people by socioeconomic variables. The task is to predict the use of health care; the environment is defined by the type of health insurance. Details can be found in Nastl & Hardt (2024).

Experimental Details: The candidate rules for the models (\mathcal{R}) are thresholds on the value of single features (a.k.a. decision stumps). For each feature, we consider up to 50 thresholds, obtained by quantizing the range of values it takes across the training set. Then, for each feature and threshold, two rules are defined: the first returns “True” if the feature’s value is above the threshold and “False” otherwise; the second is the negation of the first. The maximum size of conjunctions is set to $n = 10$. For each dataset, we randomly split the data into two halves—the training and testing sets—and repeat this 20 times.

The set of candidate rules \mathcal{R} must be chosen before running the SCM algorithm and depends on the nature of the data. In the case of Boolean-valued attributes, i.e. $\mathbf{x} \in \{0, 1\}^n$ it is natural to define one rule per attribute ($r_k(\mathbf{x}) = x_k$ for $k = 1, \dots, n$). In the case of continuous real-valued attributes, i.e., $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, it is common in many learning algorithms (as decision trees) to define rules as decision stumps, that relies on a attribute index $k = 1, \dots, n$, a threshold values $t \in \mathbf{R}$ and a direction $d \in \{-1, 1\}$ such that $r(\mathbf{x})_{k,t,d} = x_k \geq t$ if $d = 1$ and $r(\mathbf{x})_{k,t,d} = x_k < t$ otherwise. The size of the set \mathcal{R} impacts the computing time linearly.

Results: We compare ICSCM to its non-causal counterpart, SCM, based on two factors: (i) the ability to identify causal features and (ii) the prediction error of models.

First, we compare the number of causal features used by each algorithm as a function of model size. To support the ability to identify causal features *better than chance*, we include a random baseline corresponding to the expected number of causal variables that would have been selected by a random pick without replacement. This is simply the expectation of a hypergeometric distribution with parameters derived from Table 1. The results, averaged over 20 trials, are illustrated in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Number of causal features discovered as a function of the model size (feature rank) for real-world datasets. The solid lines give the average causal feature count over 20 repetitions, and the shaded areas report the standard errors. The gray dashed line indicates the expected number of causal variables selected by a random pick. The detailed behavior of each model is shown in supplementary Figure 5.

Overall, we observe that, for $n = 10$, ICSCM identifies more causal features than SCM for 4/6 datasets and that both methods are on par for 1/6 datasets. Note that it is not surprising that SCM also relies on causal features sometimes, as these may be good predictors of Y . Finally, note that

ICSCM identifies more causal features than the random baseline for 4/6 datasets, while the SCM does so for 2/6 datasets. Qualitatively, we observe that ICSCM generally tends to keep selecting causal features as the model size increases, while the number of causal features selected by the SCM could stagnate once a certain count is reached.

Second, we assess the test error of the models learned using SCM and ICSCM. The results, averaged over 20 trials, are presented in Table 2. Overall, SCM tends to build models that are slightly more accurate than those of ICSCM. This is in line with the observations of Hardt & Kim (2022), which showed that using only causal variables leads to reduced predictive accuracy, emphasizing a tradeoff between understanding and predicting. Yet, the accuracy of ICSCM models does not differ drastically from those of SCM.

Given that real datasets are likely to break the assumptions underlying ICSCM, these results exhibit a good tendency, showing that the modifications proposed to the original SCM algorithms favor the discovery of causal variables.

A.8 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The code for all the experiments is available at: <https://github.com/thibgo/icscm-experiments>.

A.9 BASELINES AND IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

For the Set Covering Machine (SCM) and classification tree (DT) baselines, as well as ICSCM, we conducted a hyperparameter search using 5-fold cross-validation and selected the values that led to the highest binary accuracy, on average, over all folds. Details are provided below:

- Set Covering Machine (SCM; Marchand & Shawe-Taylor (2002)): We used the implementation available at <https://github.com/aldro61/pyscm> (version 1.1.0) and considered the following hyperparameter values for trade-off p : $\{0.1, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 2.5, 5, 10\}$. The models built were conjunctions.
- Classification trees (DT; Breiman et al. (1984)): We used the implementation available in Scikit-Learn (version 1.2.2; Pedregosa et al. (2011)) and considered the following hyperparameter values: i) maximum depth: $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 10\}$, ii) minimum samples split: $\{2, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.3\}$.
- ICSCM: We implemented the pseudo-code showed in Algorithm 2 in Python and considered the following hyperparameter values for utility p : $\{0.1, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 2.5, 5, 10\}$. The models built were conjunctions. Conditional independence was tested using a χ^2 test with $\alpha = 0.05$. For the pruning procedure, we used the conditional G-test implementation available at <https://github.com/keiichishima/gsq>, also with $\alpha = 0.05$.

For the ICP baseline, we reimplemented the method in Heinze-Deml et al. (2018). The implementation is available in our main codebase. Conditional independence was tested using a conditional G test with $\alpha = 0.05$. We used the conditional G-test implementation available at <https://github.com/keiichishima/gsq>.

A.10 DETAILED RESULTS OF REAL-WORLD DATA EXPERIMENTS

The Fig. 5 shows the 20 individual curves of SCM and ICSCM that are averaged in Fig. 4. The Table 3 extends the results of Table 2 by including the standard deviation over 20 repetitions.

A.11 ROBUSTNESS TO TYPE I AND TYPE II ERRORS

While algorithms like ICP and ICSCM offer strong theoretical guarantees, their empirical performance is subject to the reliability of the (conditional) independence tests that they perform. Empirical phenomena such as *type I* errors (false positive: finding dependence when there is none) and *type II* errors (false negative: finding independence when there is dependence) can affect their performance in practice. Type I errors can be controlled via the α threshold on the p-value of the statistical tests. However, type II errors are more difficult to control, as the false negative rate β depends on the statistical power of a test, which in turn depends on factors such as the effect size

Figure 5: Detailed behavior of the models on each split, showing the number of causal variables selected.

Table 3: Prediction error of the models averaged on the 20 splits. The standard deviation is indicated in parentheses.

	Train		Test	
	SCM	ICSCM	SCM	ICSCM
acsfoodstamps	0.19 (0.0017)	0.19 (0.0050)	0.19 (0.0007)	0.19 (0.0044)
acsincome	0.27 (0.0013)	0.32 (0.0222)	0.27 (0.0010)	0.32 (0.0225)
assistments	0.07 (0.0005)	0.11 (0.0299)	0.07 (0.0001)	0.11 (0.0298)
college scorecard	0.08 (0.0006)	0.11 (0.0060)	0.08 (0.0007)	0.11 (0.0059)
diabetes readmission	0.38 (0.0016)	0.46 (0.0058)	0.38 (0.0015)	0.46 (0.0052)
meps	0.26 (0.0028)	0.33 (0.0357)	0.27 (0.0030)	0.34 (0.0328)

Table 4: Identification of the causal parents \mathbf{X}_A : proportion of 100 training runs where the model relied solely on \mathbf{X}_A , for an increasing number of distractor features \mathbf{X}_B (1 to 200).

\mathbf{X}_B	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	10	15	20	25	50	100	200
ICSCM	0.96	0.97	0.99	0.96	0.97	0.96	0.96	0.89	0.89	0.86	0.96	0.90	0.91	0.94

(which we do not control) and the number of available data samples. Here, we discuss the effect of each type of error on both algorithms.

ICP: To find the set of causal parents \mathbf{X}_A , ICP tests the independence of Y and E conditioned on every possible set of variables, resulting in $2^{|\mathbf{X}|}$ conditional independence tests. Then, the algorithm takes the intersection of all sets that were found to lead to independence (see Heinze-Deml et al. (2018), line 4 of Algorithm 1 in Appendix B). The intersection has an effect similar to the pruning procedure of ICSCM (see Proposition 3.2) and serves to filter out \mathbf{X}_B from the solution. ICP is quite robust to type I errors since such errors result in discarding only a few of the sets that contain \mathbf{X}_A . Apart from rare cases, such as making a type I error for the set $\{\mathbf{X}_A\}$ and not for all sets containing both \mathbf{X}_A and \mathbf{X}_B , the intersection renders the algorithm robust to type I errors. On the other hand, ICP is vulnerable to type II errors, which can cause it to incorrectly include a set that does not lead to independence, e.g., $\{\mathbf{X}_C\}$ or $\{X_{A1}\}$ (but missing some $X_{Ai} \in \mathbf{X}_A$) in the intersection. If this happens, the intersection returns either the empty set or a partial set of causal parents. As the dimensionality of \mathbf{X} increases (for a fixed sample size), the power of the statistical tests decreases and the probability β of making such errors increases, amplifying the problem. We hypothesize that this is what causes the poor performance of ICP for the larger sizes of \mathbf{X}_B at Fig. 2a. This is supported by the results at Fig. 6, which show that the *recall* of ICP on the task of identifying the set of causal parents drops for $|\mathbf{X}_B| \geq 6$. In contrast, note that the *precision* remains stable (see Fig. 6), illustrating the robustness of this method to type I errors.

Figure 6: Precision and recall metrics on the task of identifying the set of causal parents for ICP and ICSCM. The scores are computed for several values of $|\mathbf{X}_B|$, and averaged over 100 randomly generated datasets, using the experimental design presented in App. A.6.

ICSCM: We separate the discussion of how ICSCM can be affected by type I and II errors into three parts, based on the different stages of the algorithm. For simplicity, let us assume that the set of candidate rules \mathcal{R} contains a single rule per causal parent.

1. **Effect on Eq. (1):** This criterion is used to select which rules are permitted to be added to the model. A type I error has the effect of rejecting a rule that actually satisfies the criterion, e.g., rejecting a causal parent in \mathbf{X}_A . If this happens, the resulting conjunction might not contain all the causal parents. However, note that, even if a causal parent is rejected at one stage of building the conjunction, the data filtering that occurs at the end of every iteration in Algorithm 2 results in re-testing the same rule with a subset of the data at the next iteration, which might offer some resistance to type I errors. As for type II errors, these correspond to incorrectly believing that the criterion is satisfied and could result in adding rules that depend on \mathbf{X}_C to the conjunction. In both cases, if such errors were to be made, the stopping criterion at Eq. (2) would not be satisfiable due to unblocked paths between Y and E in G . In terms of precision and recall w.r.t. the causal parents, type I and type II errors would result in lower recall and precision, respectively.
2. **Effect on Eq. (2):** This criterion is used to determine when to stop adding rules to the model. Here, a type I error would result in a failure to stop. However, note that, even if the algorithm failed to stop, as long as all R_i have been added to the conjunction, the algorithm should find that no other R_j satisfies Eq. (1) and stop, offering some robustness to such errors. As for type II errors, these would result in incorrectly concluding that the criterion is satisfied, resulting in premature stopping and missing causal parents in \mathbf{X}_A . Hence, type I and type II errors would result in lower precision and recall, respectively.
3. **Effect on Proposition 3.2:** This result is the foundation for the pruning procedure of ICSCM. Here, a type I error would result in incorrectly keeping a variable in \mathbf{X}_B in the conjunction instead of pruning it. In contrast, a type II error would result in incorrectly removing a variable in \mathbf{X}_A from the conjunction. Type I and type II errors would therefore result in lower precision and recall, respectively.

Finally, note that while we typically cannot control all the factors that govern type II errors (β), there is one key element that distinguishes ICSCM from ICP: ICP must conduct conditional independence testing for every possible set of parents, resulting in large conditioning sets. In contrast, ICSCM's tests are only conditioned on a number of variables that grows linearly with the length of the conjunction. As such, ICSCM's tests may have greater power and the algorithm may be less affected by type II errors. The results at Fig. 6, show that both the precision and recall of ICSCM remain high as the number of variables increases, in contrast with ICP whose recall decreases significantly.